

ABSTRACT

The International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) is aimed at enabling data exchange of image data and their description and annotation via software interfaces (APIs). Digital scholarly editions share this overarching objective, but focus mostly on data transmitted in textual form. The advantages of using IIIF have been discussed for some time under the keyword "Distributed Editions". The two-day workshop is intended to enable an exchange between developers of IIIF applications in libraries and digital scholarly editors.

FUNDING

CLARIAH-AT, ÖAW, FWF Project "History as a Visual Concept" (I 6133)

REGISTRATION

Participation is free, but as room capacity is limited we ask for registration: Contact Roman Bleier, roman.bleier@uni-graz.at or Stephan Kurz, stephan.kurz@oeaw.ac.at until April 11, 2025.

WWW.OEAW.AC.AT

ÖAW

AUSTRIAN
ACADEMY OF
SCIENCES

7-8 MAY 2025
PSK BUILDING
3RD FLOOR, ROOM 1+2
GEORG-COCH-PLATZ 2
1010 VIENNA

D. Ambrosii Varia. Florencia. Biblioteca Medicea Laurenziana, Plut.14.23 (manuscript, 15th century)

WORKSHOP

IIIF IN/AND DIGITAL SCHOLARLY EDITIONS

PROGRAMME

MAY 7, 2025 – DATA PROVIDERS

- 12:00–13:00 **Opening remarks**
Introduction round
- Lydia Eder (IHB/ÖAW)**
Introduction: IIF resources in the CLARIAH-AT framework
- 13:00–14:30 **Session 1**
Torsten Schaßan (Herzog-August-Bibliothek Wolfenbüttel)
Usage of IIF for digital facsimiles and digital editions at the HAB
- Johannes Knüchel, Christoph Steindl (ÖNB)**
The IIF services of the Austrian National Library
- Christiane Fritze (Wienbibliothek im Rathaus)**
IIF application in the Vienna City Library
- 14:30–15:00 BREAK
- 15:00–16.30 **Session 2**
Barbara Tramelli (Freie Universität Bozen)
The use of IIF in the Biblissima collections: future perspectives for the project 'Le livre illustré à Lyon (1480–1600)'
- Leander Seige (Leipzig University Library)**
IIF and Persistent Identifiers: Foundations for Cross-Institutional Scholarly Work
- Roman Bleier, Jakob Sonnberger (University of Graz)**
IIF and GAMS Projects: Peter of Poitiers' Compendium Historiae as Example
- 16:30–17:00 COFFEE BREAK
- 17:00–18.00 **Evening Lecture**
Glen Robson (Technical Coordinator, IIF Consortium)
IIF Developments and interesting implementations
- Discussion**
- 19:00 DINNER
Elvira's Restaurant, Seidlgasse 39, 1030 Wien

MAY 8, 2025 – TOOLS AND APPLICATIONS

- 09:00–10:30 **Session 3**
Dario Kampkaspar (ULB Darmstadt/Transkribus)
From Raw Data to Digital Editions using IIF: Preparing and Publishing with Transkribus Sites
- Peter Andorfer (ACDH-CH/ÖAW)**
How the ACDH-CH uses IIF (not only) for digital scholarly editions
- Rainer Simon**
*Real-time collaborative annotation with *liiiv**
- 10:30–11:00 COFFEE BREAK
- 11:00–12:30 **Session 4**
Martina Bürgermeister (ÖNB)
Use cases of IIF in the Digital Scholarly Editions infrastructure of the Austrian National Library
- Nicolas Renet, Florian Atzenhofer-Baumgartner (Uni Graz)**
IIF for Historical Document Analysis: Approaches to Machine Learning and Image Annotation Workflows in Monasterium.net
- Participants' projects**
- 12:30–13:30 **Closing remarks**

German language short documentation on IIF is available at <https://www.ditah.at/iif/>